

ETHNOBOTANIC INFORMATION IN SCIENTIFIC MEDICINE

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Abstract: The article reveals the role of the use of medicinal plants in traditional medicine. The types of medicinal and honey plants of Uzbekistan are analyzed and the resources of raw materials of promising medicinal and honey plants are estimated.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, botanical research, diseases, inventory

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Introduction In maintaining the health of the population, treatment and prevention of morbidity, along with other major factors, timely provision of medical, sanitary and preventive institutions and the population with highly effective drugs is of great importance. This problem is solved mainly through the production or purchase of well-known, long-used medicines and the creation of new effective medicines. Medicinal plants play a special role as sources of new medicines. Plants and their products have always been and remain the main remedies of folk and traditional medicine. Since people began to use the blessings of nature from time immemorial, they have come up with the use of medicinal herbs in the treatment of diseases. More than 3-4 thousand years ago, in the countries of India, China, Ancient Egypt, there were written works that provide information about medicinal plants. In the East, especially in Central Asian folk medicine, treatment using medicinal herbs has its own ancient traditions. In the work of Abu Ali Ibn Sina "Al-Kanun" about the use of medicinal plants for medical purposes, information about the healing properties of about 476 plants and the methods of their use is presented. At present, the type of medicinal plants is increased, folk medicine is enriched with medicinal plants. The plant world of our country consists of 659 varieties and more than 4800 species belonging to 115 families. As a result of botanic research, which has a history of one and a half centuries in Uzbekistan, huge reserves of information on the colorful world of plants have been collected. The six-volume book "Flora of Uzbekistan" (1941-1962) contains 3663 species of plants (3824 with introducents). As a result of the joint

research of a large group of specialists, the book "description of plants of Central Asia", 10 drops, was published in 1963-1993. This book is one of the main sources about the diversity of plants in Uzbekistan so far [3].

It should be noted that in recent years, Botanical research naprevleny to identify food-valuable groups of plants, assessment of their resources, ethnobotanical research, determination of the composition of medicinal plants in the regions, the establishment of honey species, and their introduction into production will serve to meet the needs of the population in medicinal and food products. Accordingly, the inventory of medicinal and melliferous plants, preparation of synopsis, identifying the stock of promising types and possible areas of their duties, classification of medicinal plants according to groups of diseases have important scientific and practical value, practical use, and develop measures for their protection. Currently, the increase in population leads to an increase in demand for both medicinal plants and natural honey and bee products. In the world there are more than 20,000 types of dangerous diseases for human health, in the treatment of which more than 15,000 drugs are used. In the manufacture of such drugs, about 3000 names of raw materials are used, more than 35% of which are obtained from plants. In this regard, the inventory of species of medicinal plants, assessment of their resources and identification of promising species for production are topical issues [4]. With the independence of our Republic, large-scale reforms were carried out on the inventory of plants of important economic value, in this regard, special attention was paid to the use of available medicinal plants, the cultivation of honey plants. On the basis of the program measures implemented in this direction, significant results have been achieved, in particular, on the creation of pharmaceutical zones specialized in the cultivation of medicinal plants, the expansion of the range of medicinal and honey plants and the creation of their raw material base. Ethnobotanical data on regional medicinal plants and their use in folk medicine are given in the works of foreign scientists Nidal A. Jaradat (2005), E. A. Singh, S. Y. Kamble, N. K. Bipinraj, S. D. Jagtap (2012), Ram Prakash (2014). In the CIS countries, studies on biological features, application, systematic, chemical composition and distribution are covered in the scientific works of scientists O. Dadabayev (1996), G. M. Berdimuhamedov (2010), N. G. Gemedzhiev (2012) , etc. Data on medicinal and partially honey-bearing plants growing in natural conditions on the territory of Karakalpakstan are given in the studies of S. E. Erezhepov (1971), on the distribution of medicinal plants by A. Bakhiev and others (1983) and on the stocks of medicinal plants in the works of S. Dauletmuratov (1991). In the works of G. Zh. Abdiniyazova (2017) [1] identified species of medicinal and honey plants of Karakalpakstan and given an assessment of raw material resources of promising medicinal and honey plants. It should be noted that for the first time a list of 444 species of medicinal plants of Karakalpakstan

belonging to 240 genera, 63 families and 207 species of honey plants belonging to 125 genera, 42 families was compiled, and the identical use of 46% of medicinal plants in scientific and folk medicine of the CIS and East Asia was revealed; the reserves of raw materials for 8 species of medicinal and 5 species of honey plants were determined. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. These are used in scientific and folk medicine from about 120 plant species that grow and cultured in natural conditions. At present, about 40-47% of the aging of medicines used in medicine are taken from plant chamomile. Herb is used in the form of medicinal herbs of dried herbs, from dried herbs, buds, roots, rhizomes, endings, onions, bark, leaves, flowers, buds, fruits (seeds), , juice, lard, licorice, essential oil and other(s) [2] It is worth noting that medical plants are classified into 2 types: 1) depending on the composition of the causative agents - alkaloid, glycoside, oil of ether, vitamin and other(s); 2) depending on the pharmacological indicators - soothing, analgesic, sleeping, affecting the cardiovascular system, excitation of the central nervous system, lowering blood pressure, etc. The causative agents of medicinal plants can be alkaloids, various glycosides, flavonoids, coumarins, excipients and mucous substances, ether oils, vitamins, dye substances, trace elements, phytoncides, starch, proteins, polysaccharides, nitrogenous substances, fatty and fatty acids and other(s) compounds. The effect of medicinal plants on the body depends on the amount of chemical compounds contained in it. These compounds accumulate in different quantities in parts of the plant. The period of high potency and quality of medicinal plants corresponds to the time of their flowering and the beginning of the fertilization period. Medical substances accumulate in the buds, leaves or stems of some plants, in the flowers or fruits of some plants, in some-in the roots or bark. Therefore, a large part of plants, mainly biologically active substances, is harvested. The root of the plant, the rhizome, the onion and the ending are usually prepared in the early spring, when the plant is asleep - in late autumn or before the plant Awakens. Fruits and seeds of the plant are harvested when ripening, because they are rich in medicinal substances at this time. The newly harvested medical herb is moist in the composition of the crop (85% in the upper members of the Earth, 45% in the pot). If this moisture is not lost (by drying), the plant will rot, the medicinal substances will decompose and become unusable.

It is known that drugs that are prepared on the basis of medicinal herbs, including medicinal tinctures, have a number of advantages, which are expressed in the following: - hooliganism (low toxicity) with the corresponding effectiveness of the drug); - their" ointment " permanent effect; - availability of quick and easy preparation options; - no special complex technological equipment required; - cheapness and others [5]. The population of Bukhara has unique information about the use of medicinal plants in folk medicine. The rich experience of traditional

medicine is lost due to the natural loss of carriers of this information, since most of the keepers of this knowledge are the oldest inhabitants of villages. It is necessary to intensify the efforts of biologists, physicians and all interested professionals in the collection and processing of ethno-botanical information in order to preserve knowledge and use it in the future in scientific medicine.

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